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Research

**ANALYSIS OF MECHANISM OF GENETIC POLYMORPHISMS AND
ITS ASSOCIATION OF BLOOD TRANSFUSION IN ACUTE MYELOID
LEUKEMIA AMONG LOCAL POPULATION OF PAKISTAN**

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Abstract:

Introduction: Acute myeloid leukemia (AML) is a heterogeneous group of leukemias that result from the clonal transformation of a primitive stem/progenitor cell by more than one genetic aberration. **Aims of the study:** The main objective of the study is to analyze the mechanism of genetic polymorphisms and its association of blood transfusion in acute myeloid leukemia among local population of Pakistan. **Methodology of the study:** This descriptive study was conducted in PIMS, Islamabad during November 2018 to March 2019. The data was collected from histologically confirmed cases of AML. The age group for this data was 20 to 50 years. Participation of all the patients were voluntary and written consent was obtained from all participants. Those who want to participate and signed consent were interviewed by medical staff by using a standardized and structured questionnaire and personal interview. **Results:** The data was collected from 50 patients of AML. There is a positive correlation between blood transfusion and AML B-cells. Table 02 represents the data of both normal cases and AML patients. **Conclusion:** It is concluded that genetic polymorphism in TNF and IL10RA gene modifies the association between blood transfusion and risk of leukemia B-cells.

Key words: Acute, Transfusion, Blood, Genes

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INTRODUCTION:

Acute myeloid leukemia (AML) is a heterogeneous group of leukemias that result from the clonal transformation of a primitive stem/progenitor cell by more than one genetic aberration. The ALL cells carry numerous genetic alterations with specific prognostic value. Therefore, their description is an important part of the diagnostic procedure, not only for choice of risk adapted treatment, but also because some of the altered proteins can be subjected to highly efficient targeted therapy [1]. It represents 20– 25% of all youth intense leukemias and is in charge of more than one-portion of the leukemia passings. Current pediatric AML conventions result in 85%–90% finish reduction rates, with long haul survival rates for patients who accomplish abatement in the scope of 60%– 70% and occasion free survival rates in the vicinity of 45% and 55% [2]. This has made conceivable because of the heightening of chemotherapy, better hazard amass stratification, expanded utilization of allogeneic hematopoietic undifferentiated cell transplantation, and enhancements in strong care [3]. Nonetheless, protection from chemotherapy remains a noteworthy reason for treatment disappointment among pediatric patients with AML, with unfavorable symptoms adding to bleakness and mortality [4].

Cytarabine (1- β -D-arabinofuranosylcytosine, Ara-C) is a basic simple of deoxycytidine (dCyd) and has been the pillar of treatment for AML for over four decades. It is a hydrophilic atom that requires encouraged dispersion by means of nucleoside-particular layer transport bearers [5]. To enter the cell, Ara-C ties to the human equilibrative nucleoside transporter (hENT1), in any case, when regulated at high

measurements, the medication can be taken up by uninvolved dispersion. Inside the cell, Ara-C is phosphorylated to monophosphate (Ara-CMP) by deoxycytidine kinase (dCK); subsequently, two further phosphorylations are catalyzed by pyrimidine kinases to change over Ara-CMP into the dynamic metabolite ara-cytidine-5'-triphosphate (Ara-CTP) [6].

Aims of the study

The main objective of the study is to analyze the mechanism of genetic polymorphisms and its association of blood transfusion in acute myeloid leukemia among local population of Pakistan.

METHODOLOGY OF THE STUDY:

This descriptive study was conducted in PIMS, Islamabad during November 2018 to March 2019. The data was collected from histologically confirmed cases of AML. The age group for this data was 20 to 50 years. Participation of all the patients were voluntary and written consent was obtained from all participants. Those who want to participate and signed consent were interviewed by medical staff by using a standardized and structured questionnaire and personal interview.

Statistical analysis

The data was collected and analyzed using SPSS version 20.0. All *P* values presented in the results are two-sided, and all analyses were performed by using SAS software.

RESULTS:

The data was collected from 50 patients of AML. Table 01 represent the data of study population in which we explains the age, family history of blood transfusion and consumption of alcohol. We also collect the data of diffuse large beta cell lymphoma.

Table1: Selected characteristics of study population

Characteristics	Cases	N=482	%	p-value
Age				
<50	146		30.3	0.07
50-70	170		35.7	
≥70	166		34.0	
Family history of blood transfusion				
Yes	76		9.7	0.02
No	406		81.3	
Consumption of alcohol				
Yes	169		35.1	0.19
No	313		64.9	
Smoking				
Yes	211		43.8	0.40
No	271		56.2	
DLBL	115		31.1	-
FL	82		2.6	
CLL	285		56.2	

DLBL=diffuse large B-cell lymphoma, FL=follicular lymphoma, CLL=chronic lymphocytic leukemia.

There is a positive correlation between blood transfusion and AML B-cells. Table 02 represents the data of both normal cases and AML patients.

Table 2: Association between blood transfusion and leukemia B-cells

Blood transfusion	Overall			B-cell lymphoma	
	Control	Case	OR(95% CI)	Case	OR(95% CI)
No	124	98	1.0	311	1.0
Yes	417	384	0.9 (0.7–1.2)	75	0.8 (0.6–1.2)
	DLBCL			CLL	
Blood transfusion	Control	Case	OR(95% CI)	Case	OR(95% CI)
No	124	29	1.0	78	1.0
Yes	417	121	0.9 (0.6–1.4)	26	0.7 (0.4–1.2)

DLBL=diffuse large B-cell lymphoma, CLL=chronic lymphocytic leukemia.

DISCUSSION:

Acute Lymphoblastic Leukemia (ALL) is a heterogeneous group of disorders that result from the clonal proliferation and expansion of malignant lymphoid cells in the bone marrow, blood and other organs. It is the most common type of cancer in children and adolescents accounting for 23-25% of all malignant diseases. Recent clinical studies have suggested that local bone marrow angiogenesis with increased blood vessel density is important both for disease development and chemo-sensitivity in acute leukemias [7]. Many studies have shown that patients with leukemia and lymphoma have increased micro-vascularity as well as increased levels of pro-angiogenic vascular growth factors, including VEGF [8].

There are many evidences highlight the significant biological role of the VEGF-C/VEGF-R3 axis in vascular endothelial cells [9]. The VEGF has an important role in the induction of neovascularization, thereby promoting tumor growth and metastatic potential. Besides that, autocrine and paracrine VEGF/VEGF-related loops were described in hematological malignancies such as acute and chronic leukemia, myelodysplastic syndromes, myeloproliferative neoplasms, lymphomas and multiple myeloma [10].

CONCLUSION

It is concluded that genetic polymorphism in TNF and IL10RA gene modifies the association between blood transfusion and risk of leukemia B-cells.

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